

Some notes and experiments on the electropermeabilization of viral membranes

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Summary

It has been suggested that the charge distribution and solvent damping of some species of viruses might offer some scope for inactivation by extreme electric fields, through mechanisms similar to - but distinct from - well-established bilayer electroporation effects.

A series of haphazard experiments on bacteriophage T4 have yielded no novel results. With a field of 10^6 V/m in the nanosecond pulse regime and 10^2 V/m in the microsecond pulsed 6 to 12 GHz regime, we have not replicated the conditions or results of previous studies, especially considering the lack of a lipid envelope in the chosen surrogate. A generous reader might regard this as a negative result. Pulse shaping, a central interest of this study, was not employed due to a lack of diagnostic equipment.

Due to wide error bars and an unhealthy preoccupation with methodology and instrumentation, we have not been able to contribute even a tenuous theoretical or experimental basis for, or against, such an effect. It is hoped that this work will be of some small use in suggesting some lines of inquiry for future efforts, and in reporting some pitfalls encountered.

Optimization suggests that in certain cases, due to the Brillouin precursors, the minimum-amplitude waveform to maximally drive the virion when propagated through a lossy, dispersive medium like tissue may be simply a saw-tooth.

Modifications to existing irreversible electroporation therapies may be plausible; some precedent also exists for more far fetched routes such as optical centrifuge and electrorotation; but we have not studied these techniques in any depth and have no reason to believe that they can be made practical or effective.

Given that every avenue pursued consumes precious resources and attention, together with the TRL 0 nature of the effect, in retrospect, this was probably not a good use of time.

An entirely free and open-source software toolchain was used for the majority of the project, and all instruments required are relatively inexpensive to build; and so the results are hopefully replicable by any interested workers.

This document is not peer-reviewed and should not be taken seriously.

More experimental details, a categorized reference database for convenience, the (admittedly garbage) codebase, and a few other notes and lessons learned will be available at github.com/0xDBFB7/covidinator. We hope to add more details and discussion (first-principles culture protocols, operation of the spectrometer and scan-converter). Criticism on content and comprehensibility is invited; either via email, [a public forum](#), or the GitHub issues page.

We regret that this document is written in a terse and inaccessible format at a time when clear and broadly understandable language is particularly important^a, and apologize for any misinterpretation that this may cause. The effects discussed are implausible in anything but the most controlled clinical situations, and would never be encountered in any existing setting.

^a"Re: Covid 19: NEJM and former CDC director launch stinging attacks on US response", en, [m3925 \(2021\)](#).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

- (a) *Chengxiang* nanosecond pulse exposure jig. Aluminum disc belongs to the scan-conversion digitizer, not used in this study.
 (b) Pulsed X-Band microwave spectrometer used.
 (c) Simulation of a (largely ineffective) bronchoscopic method.
 (d) FDTD simulation geometry of the 0.2 mm coplanar waveguide exposure cell.
 (e) The very pretty opalescent blue culture caused by *E. coli* B uptake of X-Gal.
 (f) Fluorescence reader used.

0.1 Data from testing on bacteriophage T4

Calibration trials		
Exposure	kilocounts per 10s integration	Note #
Autoclaved phage (0.2 mL)	30	Run 8
Autoclaved p. (50 uL)	32	
Phage culture 'blank'	8	
Water	1	
Pulsed CW trials		
NF capillary , 6 to 12 GHz, 10 or 20 us CW pulses, 85 V/m to 339 V/m expected		
Sham	12	Run 8 t4,5...
+	11	Run 8 t4,5...
+	12	Run 8 t4,5...
+	12	Run 8 t4,5...
NF capillary , 6 to 12 GHz, phage degraded with basic buffer, 85 V/m to 339 V/m expected		
Blank (0 min)	14	Run 9
Blank (~15 min)	17	Run 9
Sham (~15 min)	5	Run 9
Blank (~4 hr)	24	Run 9
+	14	Run 11
Sham	17	Run 11
NF capillary , 6 to 12 GHz, 10 or 20 us CW pulses		
Sham	12	Run 12
+	10	Run 12
0.2 mm channel , 6 to 12 GHz, 10 or 20 us CW pulses, 200 V/m to 850 V/m exp., 10.6 kV/m pk		
Sham	12	CPWG micro-
+	10	CPWG micro-
Nanosecond pulsed trials		
~0.2 mm channel, various pulse counts and termination, 0.155 MV/m expected, 5.6 MV/m peak		
Blank	8	Li test 1
+	8	Li test 1
+	7	Li test 1
+	7	Li test 1
+ & shaper	7	Li test 1
~0.03 mm channel, 0.2 uL/s, various pulse counts and termination, 1 MV/m expected, 38 MV/m peak		
Sham	5	Smaller
+	6	Smaller
+	6	Smaller
~0.03 mm channel, basic buffer, tainted as pH may not have been 10.6, 1 MV/m exp., 38 MV/m pk		
Sham	12	Weakened
Blank	11	Weakened
Blank	12	Weakened
Blank	9	Weakened
+	11	Weakened
+ (no term)	11	Weakened
+	9	Weakened

Original notes for this table can be inspected at [Q/firmware/eppenwolf/pulse_1.pnw](#). Data rounded to the nearest thousand fluorescence photon counts per 10 seconds. Larger numbers are presumed to correlate with greater capsid damage (see Autoclaved).

Note the width of the electric field bounds. These are not meaningful random or systematic intervals; we can only confidently assert that the field did not exceed the peak value at any point within the channel. Expected values based on FDTD simulation and voltage; peak based on channel width and voltage.

See notes on experiment design and data collection in main body and GitHub supplemental.

A few well-established non-resonant non-thermal phenomena caused by extreme electric fields have been put to practical use.

Electroporation^[1], now a common laboratory procedure, occurs when an enormous electric field causes ions in solution to diffuse across a cell membrane, capacitively charging it, provoking a change in lipid bilayer conformation^[2], reversibly rendering the membrane permeable. This is one among many other, more subtle mechanisms; the minutia of poration can become extraordinarily complex in certain circumstances and are beyond the author's current understanding^[3].

Therapies based on irreversible electroporation^{[4][5]} have recently been used in the clinic^[6] for tumor ablation. There is much discussion on electroporation as an alternative to viral vectors, but we have found surprisingly little discussion on clinical treatment of viral infection with these conventional electroporation therapies.

However, long pulses at ≈ 10 MV/m appear to electroporate large enveloped viruses, similarly to host cells^[7], which we believe might hint that a regime of intensity, duration, and pulse count may exist to target the viral envelope. In fact, despite considering the somewhat harder problem of electroporating while inside the cell, rather than in extracellular fluid,^[8] report that 250 nm li-

posomes should be porated without inducing damage to the host cell, and modelling shows that 100 nm liposomes may be porated by 4 ns pulses never exceeding 20 MV/m. Despite the number of free parameters in pulse exposure, it is possible that scaling laws might conceivably preclude the safe formation of destructive transmembrane potentials in 100 nm-scale viruses.

The same field intensities do not appear to damage phages with protein capsids^[9], in line with our negative results on T4.

Non-resonant capsid and envelope breakage with 120 pulses, 500 ns each, at 3 MV/m, has been previously observed^[10], but the RNA damage suggests that this is an electrochemical artifact^[11] (c.f.^[12]).

However, perhaps regrettably, the experiments reported in this study were not designed to address the question of whether this conventional ion- and bilayer-driven electroporation can be harnessed, but rather to test whether purely mechanical damage from qE forces can be easily observed in viruses.

WE were inspired to undertake this project by a set of publications by a certain Sun group, (primarily Liu et al^[13] and Yang et al^[14], simultaneously demonstrated by Hung et al^[15]), partially replicated by^[16] and discussed

^[1]K. Kinoshita et al., "Electroporation of cell membrane visualized under a pulsed-laser fluorescence microscope", en, *Biophysical Journal* **53**, 1015–1019 (1988).

^[2]S. A. Kirsch and R. A. Böckmann, "Membrane pore formation in atomistic and coarse-grained simulations", en, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Biomembranes, Biosimulations of Lipid Membranes Coupled to Experiments* **1858**, 2266–2277 (2016).

^[3]M. B. Partenskii et al., "The Theoretical Challenge Posed by Low-Voltage Membrane Electroporation, Viewed from the Perspective of Continuum and Molecular-Level Models", en, *Israel Journal of Chemistry* **47**, 385–396 (2007).

^[4]A. Golberg and M. L. Yarmush, "Nonthermal Irreversible Electroporation: Fundamentals, Applications, and Challenges", en, *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* **60**, 707–714 (2013).

^[5]D. Perrier et al., "Lipid vesicles in pulsed electric fields: Fundamental principles of the membrane response and its biomedical applications", *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **249** (2017) 10.1016/j.cis.2017.04.016.

^[6]G. Narayanan et al., "Irreversible Electroporation of Hepatic Malignancy", *Seminars in Interventional Radiology* **30**, 67–73 (2013).

^[7]F. R. Madiyar et al., "AC dielectrophoretic manipulation and electroporation of vaccinia virus using carbon nanoelectrode arrays", en, *ELECTROPHORESIS* **38**, 1515–1525 (2017).

^[8]L. Retelj et al., "Electroporation of Intracellular Liposomes Using Nanosecond Electric Pulses—A Theoretical Study", en, *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* **60**, 2624–2635 (2013).

^[9]F. R. Madiyar et al., "Manipulation of bacteriophages with dielectrophoresis on carbon nanofiber nanoelectrode arrays", en, *ELECTROPHORESIS* **34**, 1123–1130 (2013).

^[10]A. Mizuno et al., "Inactivation of viruses using pulsed high electric field", in *Conference Record of the 1990 IEEE Industry Applications Society Annual Meeting* (Oct. 1990), 713–719 vol.1.

^[11]M. Sato et al., "Formation of Chemical Species and Their Effects on Microorganisms Using a Pulsed High-Voltage Discharge in Water", en, *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INDUSTRY APPLICATIONS* **32**, 7 (1996).

^[12]J.-L. Sagripanti et al., "Microwave Effects on Plasmid DNA", *Radiation Research* **110**, 219–231 (1987).

^[13]T.-M. Liu et al., "Microwave resonant absorption of viruses through dipolar coupling with confined acoustic vibrations", en, *Applied Physics Letters* **94**, 043902 (2009).

^[14]S.-C. Yang et al., "Efficient Structure Resonance Energy Transfer from Microwaves to Confined Acoustic Vibrations in Viruses", en, *Scientific Reports* **5**, 1–10 (2015).

^[15]W.-T. Hung et al., "A focusing reflectarray and its application in microwave virus sanitizer: Focusing Reflectarray", en, *Radio Science* **49**, 890–898 (2014).

^[16]J. Burkhartsmeyer et al., "Optical Trapping, Sizing, and Probing Acoustic Modes of a Small Virus", en, *Applied Sciences* **10**, 394 (2020).

^[17]N. Uzunoglu, "Theoretical Analysis of the Induction of Forced Resonance Mechanical Oscillations to Virus Particles by Microwave Irradiation: Prospects as an Anti-virus Modality", en, (2020) 10.20944/preprints202004.0462.v1.

by^[17].

These studies are all founded on the idea that some large-scale structural difference between viruses and all host cellular structures might usable as leverage to selectively inactivate the virus by some physical - rather than biological - means. For example, such an inactivation "window" between host cell and virion damage has been found in certain wavelengths of CW Far UV^[18] - but also apparently in certain modulated UV pulses^{[19][20]}, and also sporadically reported for simple thermal treatment^[21]; however, the modes exhibiting differential inactivation that have been found so far do not appear to be of particular use in the clinic.

Some possible minor shortcomings of the original experiments are due to be addressed by other groups^[22], so we try not to defer greatly to those observations.

If the duration of exposure is sufficiently short that thermal and membrane breakdown effects can be

neglected, tissue appears to withstand peak electric fields of great magnitude - above 1 nanosecond megavolt/meter, even in in-vivo studies - without severe acute effects (^{[23][24][25]} and below).

The specific concept of driving a virus as a harmonic oscillator suggested by^[26] has been previously considered only briefly^{[27][28][29][30][31]}, perhaps first because in almost all cases structures in tissue are so over-damped by the surrounding solvent^{[32][33][34][35]} as to have no non-zero resonant frequency at all^{[36][37]}^[not in citation]^[discuss]; and second, because the charge distributions found in biology are too small for energies significantly above the thermal background to be absorbed via applied fields.

On the other hand, the possibility of a slightly under-damped virion does not appear to be entirely unexpected; classical viscous Stokes drag predicts such behavior^[38] (see supplemental), and large proteins have been found with similar properties^[39]; and while MHz transverse resonances in microtubules are ruled out^[40],

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- ^[18]M. Buonanno et al., "Germicidal Efficacy and Mammalian Skin Safety of 222-nm UV Light", eng, *Radiation Research* **187**, 483–491 (2017).
- ^[19]K. Prodouz et al., "Use of laser-UV for inactivation of virus in blood products", *Blood* **70**, 589–592 (1987).
- ^[20]T. Karu, "Can Cellular Responses to Continuous-Wave and Pulsed UV Radiation Differ?", en, in *Environmental UV Photobiology*, edited by A. R. Young et al. (Springer US, Boston, MA, 1993), pp. 203–232.
- ^[21]*Summary of Proceedings of a Workshop on Serum for Tissue Culture Purposes*.
- ^[22]Y. Wang and R. Gordon, "Generating and Detecting High Frequency Liquid-Based Sound Resonances with Nanoplasmonics", en, **11**.
- ^[23]R. de Seze et al., "Repeated exposure to nanosecond high power pulsed microwaves increases cancer incidence in rat", en, *PLOS ONE* **15**, e0226858 (2020).
- ^[24]J. Juutilainen et al., "Review of possible modulation-dependent biological effects of radiofrequency fields", en, *Bioelectromagnetics* **32**, 511–534 (2011).
- ^[25]N. K. Chemeris et al., "DNA damage in frog erythrocytes after in vitro exposure to a high peak-power pulsed electromagnetic field", en, *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis* **558**, 27–34 (2004).
- ^[26]S.-C. Yang et al., "Efficient Structure Resonance Energy Transfer from Microwaves to Confined Acoustic Vibrations in Viruses", en, *Scientific Reports* **5**, 1–10 (2015).
- ^[27]P. E. Hamrick, "MECHANICAL EFFECTS OF ACOUSTIC TRANSIENTS ON TOBACCO MOSAIC VIRUS", en, PhD thesis (Medical College of Virginia, 1968).
- ^[28]L. Saviot et al., "Comment on "Estimate of the vibrational frequencies of spherical virus particles"", en, *Physical Review E* **69**, 023901 (2004).
- ^[29]E. C. Dykeman and O. F. Sankey, "Vibrational energy funneling in viruses-simulations of impulsive stimulated Raman scattering in M13 bacteriophage", eng, *Journal of Physics. Condensed Matter: An Institute of Physics Journal* **21**, 505102 (2009).
- ^[30]X. Zhou et al., "Maximum relative excitation of a specific vibrational mode via optimum laser-pulse duration", en, *Physical Review B* **82**, 075433 (2010).
- ^[31]M. A. Epstein and H. F. Cook, "The Effects of Microwaves on the Rous No. 1 Fowl Sarcoma Virus", *British Journal of Cancer* **5**, 244–251 (1951).
- ^[32]R. K. Adair, "Vibrational Resonances in Biological Systems at Microwave Frequencies", en, *Biophysical Journal* **82**, 1147–1152 (2002).
- ^[33]E. Adair and R. Petersen, "Biological effects of radiofrequency/microwave radiation", en, *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* **50**, 953–962 (2002).
- ^[34]R. K. Adair, "Biophysics Limits on the Biological Effects of Ultrawideband Electromagnetic Radiation", en, in *Radio Frequency Radiation Dosimetry and Its Relationship to the Biological Effects of Electromagnetic Fields*, edited by B. J. Klauenberg and D. Miklavčič, NATO Science Series (Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 2000), pp. 63–72.
- ^[35]K. R. Foster and J. W. Baish, "Viscous Damping of Vibrations in Microtubules", *Journal of Biological Physics* **26**, 255–260 (2000).
- ^[36]S. Gabriel et al., "The dielectric properties of biological tissues: III. Parametric models for the dielectric spectrum of tissues", en, *Physics in Medicine and Biology* **41**, 2271–2293 (1996).
- ^[37]C. Gabriel, *Compilation of the dielectric properties of body tissues at RF and microwave frequencies*. Tech. rep. (King's Coll London (United Kingdom) Dept of Physics, 1996).
- ^[38]B. N. J. Persson, "On the nature of low-frequency vibrational modes in globular protein molecules immersed in water", en, *Chemical Physics Letters* **127**, 428–431 (1986).
- ^[39]N. Miura et al., "Microwave dielectric study on bound water of globule proteins in aqueous solution", en, *Biopolymers* **34**, 357–364 (1994).
- ^[40]K. R. Foster and J. W. Baish, "Viscous Damping of Vibrations in Microtubules", *Journal of Biological Physics* **26**, 255–260 (2000).

the same arguments suggest that very weak GHz longitudinal modes may exist.

However, whether the small difference in driven amplitude between, for example, a $Q \approx 0.5$ host structure normal mode and a $Q \lesssim 6$ virion mode could possibly be of any clinical value is not clear to us.

The idea of driven oscillation in biological systems appears to have originated from work by Fröhlich^{[41][42][43][44]} on the possibility of large-scale coherent QM Bose-Einstein condensates, and then many more subtle lines of inquiry^{[45][46]}; but, to our knowledge, no such large-scale non-classical effects have ever been substantiated; specifically, suggestions of non-classical damping due to hydration layer effects have not been observed. In fact, evidence to date^{[47][48][49]} appears to agree that, not only are oscillatory effects implausible, there are no relevant, substantiated, non-diffusion-like non-thermal mechanisms.

Because the effect seen by^[50] is so striking compared to previous work in the non-thermal literature, we have tried to invent ways of explaining the observed results without invoking a non-thermal effect. Sufficient orthogonal measurements were made, so this is quite difficult. The most plausible timeline was:

- The use of microwave absorption spectroscopy techniques somewhat similar to those which have previously shown resonance-like artifacts^[51]. In particular, an effective charge of $q = 10^7 e^-$ was found via this method, which seems quite large for a 10^9 atom structure. Genome and protein charge can hardly explain $10^5 e^-$ (see below), which would be reduced further by ionic screening. It appears that the potential energy of such a sphere of charge would exceed the observed metabolic burden to build a virus by a significant factor^[52]. Ion polarization effects are generally not indicated at these timescales^[53], but faster electron polarization might occur to some small degree.
- Infrared thermography only determines the surface temperature. Based on heating patterns seen in other experiments^[54], the observed surface temperature rise does not perhaps conclusively rule out a very localized thermal effect.
- Therefore, without free-space dosimetry or simulation of power density, the frequency-selective inactivation could possibly be explained by the frequency response of the power amplifier, antenna gain, and absorption of the cuvette.

^[41]H. Fröhlich, "Long-range coherence and energy storage in biological systems: LONG-RANGE COHERENCE IN BIOLOGICAL SYSTEMS", en, *International Journal of Quantum Chemistry* **2**, 641–649 (1968).

^[42]H. Fröhlich, "Evidence for coherent excitation in biological systems", en, *International Journal of Quantum Chemistry* **23**, 1589–1595 (1983).

^[43]H. Fröhlich, "The Biological Effects of Microwaves and Related Questions", en, in *Advances in Electronics and Electron Physics*, Vol. 53, edited by L. Marton and C. Marton (Academic Press, Jan. 1980), pp. 85–152.

^[44]H. Fröhlich, "Coherence in Biology", en, in *Coherent Excitations in Biological Systems*, edited by H. Fröhlich and F. Kremer, Proceedings in Life Sciences (1983), pp. 1–5.

^[45]W. Grundler et al., "Mechanisms of electromagnetic interaction with cellular systems", en, *Naturwissenschaften* **79**, 551–559 (1992).

^[46]L. S. Taylor, "The mechanisms of athermal microwave biological effects", en, *Bioelectromagnetics* **2**, 259–267 (1981).

^[47]P. Vecchia, ed., *Exposure to high frequency electromagnetic fields, biological effects and health consequences (100 kHz - 300 GHz): review of the scientific evidence on dosimetry, biological effects, epidemiological observations, and health consequences concerning exposure to high frequency electromagnetic fields (100 kHz - 300 GHz)*, en, ICNIRP 16 (ICNIRP, Oberschleißheim, 2009).

^[48]International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP)1, "ICNIRP GUIDELINES 2020", en, *Health Physics* **118**, 483–524 (2020).

^[49]C95.1-2019, en, tech. rep. (IEEE).

^[50]S.-C. Yang et al., "Efficient Structure Resonance Energy Transfer from Microwaves to Confined Acoustic Vibrations in Viruses", en, *Scientific Reports* **5**, 1–10 (2015).

^[51]K. Foster et al., "'Resonances' in the dielectric absorption of DNA?", *Biophysical journal* **52**, 421–425 (1987).

^[52]

$$U = \frac{3}{5} \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Q^2}{R} \approx 2.3 \times 10^{-7} \text{ J} \approx 6 \times 10^{11} \text{ ATP-equivalent}$$

Mahmoudabadi (G. Mahmoudabadi et al., "Energetic cost of building a virus", en, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **114**, E4324–E4333 [2017]) provide a total per-virion energetic cost of 10^8 ATP-equivalent, so this appears to be 3 orders of magnitude too large.

Of course, much of the potential energy may have already existed in the host cell, so this is possibly a flawed comparison. If most of the charge is contributed by osmotic, ion, this potential energy may not be considered in the above. Autem: is it possible for the charged core to compensate for the potential energy of the charged shell?

^[53]International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP)1, "ICNIRP GUIDELINES 2020", en, *Health Physics* **118**, 483–524 (2020).

^[54]H. Burton, "Effects of Radio-Frequency Voltages on Bacteria", en, *Nature* **166**, 434–434 (1950).

^[55]It is interesting to consider that a field with a strong positive publication bias (Vijayalaxmi and T. J. Prihoda, "Comprehensive Review of Quality of Publications and Meta-Analysis of Genetic Damage in Mammalian Cells Exposed to Non-Ionizing Radiofrequency Fields", *Radiation Research* **191**, 20 [2018]), in the presence of stringent peer review, could unintentionally tend towards a literature populated with only the most abstruse and difficult to explain false-positive results. We do not suggest that this is relevant in this case; but a cursory review of the papers

[55]

However, if this is a thermal artifact, the fact that the spectrometry and inactivation data shown align perfectly is very difficult to explain; and so this chain of events seems unlikely.

Permeabilization at high field strengths is not necessarily completely implausible. [56] observe a similar non-ionic photoporation effect.

An interesting effect, superficially similar to the leakage found by Yang et al, has been observed on lipid liposomes similar to viral envelopes [57][58][59][60]. These results are of excellent quality, with good thermal controls. [61] This effect appears to depend on dissolved oxygen [62][63], somewhat contrary to a mechanical effect. The phase transition temperature of the lipids used (the point at which pores reseal) is also a relevant quantity.

One such report has been found to be a very strange artifact caused by the Teflon dish used for microwave trials [64], highlighting the need for exactly identical sham trials.

With [65] relatively sane choices of solvent charge screening and resonant frequency, the energy absorbed by the whole virus per cycle at 5 MV/m might vary from 10^{-5} to 100 times the thermal energy $k_b T$.

Compare to $5k_b T$ per protein for 1 capsid segment binding energy [66][67] and 6 to 30 $k_b T$ to form a single pore in a lipid bilayer [68].

With a relaxation time on the order of 500 ps, it is somewhat difficult to imagine that this energy will be sufficiently concentrated in the capsid to be destructive. After the relaxation time, only the mechanical effects that were induced can remain, unless some progressive chemical or fatigue-like degradation occurs.

Brackley [69] describe various analytic representations of the charge screening about the virion with the Poisson-Boltzmann equation; by translating the obtained charge into a steady-state Poisson simulation (ions will not migrate in nanosecond pulse timescales), a relatively representative simulation may be obtained [70].

cited in that excellent meta-analysis leads both very difficult to find fault in, and entirely disproved by later research.

[56] T. H. P. Nguyen et al., "18 GHz electromagnetic field induces permeability of Gram-positive cocci", en, *Scientific Reports* **5**, 10980 (2015).

[57] R. P. Liburdy and R. L. Magin, "Microwave-Stimulated Drug Release from Liposomes", *Radiation Research* **103**, 266–275 (1985).

[58] R. P. Liburdy et al., "The Influence of Oscillating Electromagnetic Fields on Membrane Structure and Function: Synthetic Liposome and Natural Membrane Bilayer Systems with Direct Application to the Controlled Delivery of Chemical Agents", en, 25.

[59] M. Babincová, "Correlation between Microwave-Induced Lipid Peroxidation and Liposome Leakage", en, *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung C* **49**, 139–140 (1994).

[60] L. Rems et al., "The contribution of lipid peroxidation to membrane permeability in electroporation: A molecular dynamics study", en, *Bioelectrochemistry* **125**, 46–57 (2019).

[61] One founding researcher has been implicated in a research scandal; however, the Livermore report on the topic does not appear to be public, so we cannot evaluate the basis for these claims.

[62] R. P. Liburdy and J. Vanek P. F., "Microwaves and the Cell Membrane: III. Protein Shedding Is Oxygen and Temperature Dependent: Evidence for Cation Bridge Involvement", *Radiation Research* **109**, 382–395 (1987).

[63] R. P. Liburdy et al., "Microwaves and the Cell Membrane: IV. Protein Shedding in the Human Erythrocyte: Quantitative Analysis by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography", *Radiation Research* **114**, 500–514 (1988).

[64] B. Bergqvist et al., "Effect of microwave radiation on permeability of liposomes. Evidence against non-thermal leakage", en, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects* **1201**, 51–54 (1994).

[65] The dipole spring constant can be extracted from the resonant frequency and therefore from the speed of sound and m^* , the reduced mass ($k = \omega_{res}^2 m^*$).

[66] A. Šiber et al., "Energies and pressures in viruses: contribution of nonspecific electrostatic interactions", *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **14**, 3746–3765 (2012).

[67] P. Ceres and A. Zlotnick, "Weak Protein-Protein Interactions Are Sufficient To Drive Assembly of Hepatitis B Virus Capsids", en, *Biochemistry* **41**, 11525–11531 (2002).

[68] W. F. D. Bennett et al., "Atomistic Simulations of Pore Formation and Closure in Lipid Bilayers", en, *Biophysical Journal* **106**, 210–219 (2014).

[69] C. A. Brackley et al., "Electrostatic inactivation of RNA viruses at air-water and liquid-liquid interfaces", *arXiv:2010.12530 [cond-mat, physics:physics]* (2020).

[70] implementation attempted at [Q//math/mathematica/analytic_force.nb](https://mathematica.stackexchange.com/questions/211111/implementation-attempted-at-mathematica-analytic-force-nb)

autem, discuss

At the risk of seeming a fool, what is the most useful metric for the charge quantity being discussed? We are interested in the stress produced by a certain arbitrary distribution of charge. Assuming a spherically symmetric virus composed of two charged shells, there is no intrinsic dipole moment. Polarizability or induced dipole moment are not obviously relevant; stress could be produced in an extremely stiff structure with no electron mobility. The virion has little net charge. Multipole expansions are not clearly relevant.

From a force perspective, the 10^3 genome charge easily provides the nanonewton force scale required^[71] to break capsids or envelopes in 5 MV/m fields; but accurate estimation of the capsid stress will likely require application of the Maxwell stress tensor^{[72][73]}.

On the other hand, such a sub-angstrom movement can only induce approximately a 0.05% deflection of the capsid, whereas a general value for the rupture of host cells is about 3% deflection^[74]. The stiffness of the genome could be used to explain this.

Accurately modelling this sort of multi-scale inactivation mechanism involving the collective motion of some 10^9 atoms, possibly simultaneously with fatigue from atomic dislocations^[75] and reactive oxidation effects, poses a significant computational and theoretical hassle, which has far exceeded our capabilities.

All-atom simulations of whole capsids are now possible, but existing pipelines tend to lack genome or nucleocapsid^{[76][77]} and are extremely computationally demanding.

Coarse-graining is one route out; but, as with all abstrac-

tions in simulations, the problem must be set up with great care and experience (polarizable water; proper heat-bath damping coefficients and choice of integrator)^{[78][79]}, and with an understanding of possible failure modes; we did not trust our abilities to produce correct results. An illustrative GROMACS simulation of a liposome, trajectories fourier transformed with^[80], was used to determine some parameters^[81].

Parameterizing coarse bead-spring models based on all-atom simulations of small capsid segments or proteins^[82] is another technique. In this case, DNA/RNA can be represented by homogeneous beads restrained by Lennard-Jones forces^[83]. Mechanically reasonable coarse-grained models have recently been published for SARS-CoV-2^[84]. Finite-element analysis in biology is also somewhat common^[85]; coupled finite-element and Poisson-Boltzmann^[86] seems particularly effective.

An approximate upper bound on the charge distribution due to the proteins of the virion can be obtained by multiplying primary structure charges (in our case, ex-

^[71]I. L. Ivanovska et al., "Bacteriophage capsids: Tough nanoshells with complex elastic properties", en, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **101**, 7600–7605 (2004).

^[72]L. Xiao et al., "Electrostatic forces in the Poisson-Boltzmann systems", *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **139** (2013) 10.1063/1.4819471.

^[73]M. Kummrow and W. Helfrich, "Deformation of giant lipid vesicles by electric fields", en, *Physical Review A* **44**, 8356–8360 (1991).

^[74]D. Needham and R. Hochmuth, "Electro-mechanical permeabilization of lipid vesicles. Role of membrane tension and compressibility", en, *Biophysical Journal* **55**, 1001–1009 (1989).

^[75]W. H. Roos et al., "Physical virology", en, *Nature Physics* **6**, 733–743 (2010).

^[76]J. D. Durrant et al., "Mesoscale All-Atom Influenza Virus Simulations Suggest New Substrate Binding Mechanism", en, *ACS Central Science* **6**, 189–196 (2020).

^[77]J. R. Perilla and K. Schulten, "Physical properties of the HIV-1 capsid from all-atom molecular dynamics simulations", en, *Nature Communications* **8**, 15959 (2017).

^[78]S. A. Kirsch and R. A. Böckmann, "Membrane pore formation in atomistic and coarse-grained simulations", en, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Biomembranes, Biosimulations of Lipid Membranes Coupled to Experiments* **1858**, 2266–2277 (2016).

^[79]A. R. Braun and J. N. Sachs, "Determining Structural and Mechanical Properties from Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Lipid Vesicles", en, *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **10**, 4160–4168 (2014).

^[80]M. Brehm and B. Kirchner, "TRAVIS - A Free Analyzer and Visualizer for Monte Carlo and Molecular Dynamics Trajectories", en, *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling* **51**, 2007–2023 (2011).

^[81]implemented at https://github.com/biology/simulation/GROMACS/BUMPy_bilayer/, see supplemental

^[82]A. Arkhipov et al., "Elucidating the Mechanism behind Irreversible Deformation of Viral Capsids", en, *Biophysical Journal* **97**, 2061–2069 (2009).

^[83]C. G. Myers and B. M. Pettitt, "Communication: Origin of the contributions to DNA structure in phages", *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **138** (2013) 10.1063/1.4791708.

^[84]A. Yu et al., "A Multiscale Coarse-grained Model of the SARS-CoV-2 Virion", en, *bioRxiv*, 2020.10.02.323915 (2020).

^[85]M. Bathe, "A Finite Element framework for computation of protein normal modes and mechanical response", *arXiv:0704.0634 [q-bio]* (2007).

^[86]L. Javidpour et al., "Electrostatic interaction between SARS-CoV-2 virus and charged electret fibre", *arXiv:2012.07160 [cond-mat, physics:physics]* (2020).

tracted^[87], or (^[88]) by observed protein contribution to total MW^[89], old 2D-PAGE gels^{[90][91]} (which also provides an estimate of the variation in the charge, important for accurate spectroscopy). See supplemental data. It appears that the genome charge is largely neutralized by the nucleocapsid.

It might be possible to extract the charge directly from whole-virion CryoEM maps, enabled by the charge-sensitive nature of the technique^{[92][93]}. This has not yet been implemented in any software tools and seems quite tricky.

In our cursory testing, Bacteriophage T4 did not appear to be lysed by 10 microsecond pulses between 6 and 12 GHz at about 10^2 to 10^3 V/m, nor, exploring non-resonant inactivation, did nanosecond pulses up to a few MV/m appear to have any effect. Note that neither of these regimes overlap with the results of the previous studies.

In terms of host safety, Pakhomov^[94] find no non-thermal effects on functioning frog heart pacemaker cells at 0.9 MV/m (although the field inside the tissue was not measured and could have been lower). Excellent recent *in vivo* data by de Seze following continuous exposure to nanosecond pulse trains at an external field

up to 3 MV/m^[95] notes little acute effects, but a massive rate of long-term carcinogenicity.

In-vitro, there appears to be a consistent set of effects of nanosecond pulses, or nsPEF, distinct from membrane effects, that occur on small intracellular organelles (see reviews^{[96][97]}),^[98],

In almost all recently updated standards, the precautionary 100 kV/m instantaneous field limits established by ANSI have been abolished due to a lack of evidence of harm; an excellent review in this regime is^[99]. Field limits are now generally set only by integrated pulse energy.

Previous field limits were generally set by the microwave hearing effect, a primarily thermoelastic mechanical^[100]. Thermoelastic effects can cause damage^[102], particularly when susceptors are implanted^[103], but do not seem to be a significant concern in most cases^[104].

In general, methods targeting small proteins seem to require impractical fields^[105]. Very recently, a region of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein has been reported to be susceptible to electric fields^[106]; however the field intensity required appears to be on the order of 3 GV/m.

^[87]A. S. Holehouse et al., "CIDER: Resources to Analyze Sequence-Ensemble Relationships of Intrinsically Disordered Proteins", en, *Biophysical Journal* **112**, 16–21 (2017).

^[88]E. Qin, "A complete sequence and comparative analysis of a SARS-associated virus (Isolate BJ01)", en, *Chinese Science Bulletin* **48**, 941 (2003).

^[89]J. S. Oxford et al., "Quantitative analysis of the protein composition of influenza A and B viruses using high resolution SDS polyacrylamide gels", en, *Journal of Biological Standardization* **9**, 483–491 (1981).

^[90]M. L. Privalsky and E. E. Penhoet, "Influenza virus proteins: identity, synthesis, and modification analyzed by two-dimensional gel electrophoresis.", en, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **75**, 3625–3629 (1978).

^[91]E. E. Penhoet, "The Structure and Synthesis of Influenza Virus Phosphoproteins", en, 9.

^[92]J. Wang et al., "Identification of ions in experimental electrostatic potential maps", *IUCrJ* **5**, 375–381 (2018).

^[93]C. A. Brackley et al., "Electrostatic inactivation of RNA viruses at air-water and liquid-liquid interfaces", *arXiv:2010.12530 [cond-mat, physics:physics]* (2020).

^[94]A. G. Pakhomov et al., "Comparative effects of extremely high power microwave pulses and a brief CW irradiation on pacemaker function in isolated frog heart slices", en, **10**.

^[95]R. de Seze et al., "Repeated exposure to nanosecond high power pulsed microwaves increases cancer incidence in rat", en, *PLOS ONE* **15**, e0226858 (2020).

^[96]T. Schunck et al., "Penetration and propagation into biological matter and biological effects of high-power ultra-wideband pulses: a review", en, *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine* **35**, 84–101 (2016).

^[97]T. Batista Napotnik et al., "Effects of high voltage nanosecond electric pulses on eukaryotic cells (in vitro): A systematic review", en, *Bioelectrochemistry* **110**, 1–12 (2016).

^[98]A.G. Pakhomov, *Bioeffects of Extremely High Peak Power, Ultra-Short Electric Field Pulses*.

^[99](N. A. T. ORGANIZATION, "NATO Research Task Group 189", [2018]), as cited by C95.1-2019, B.4.3 Rationale for pulsed RF field limits.^[100]

^[101]A. W. Guy et al., "MICROWAVE-INDUCED ACOUSTIC EFFECTS IN MAMMALIAN AUDITORY SYSTEMS AND PHYSICAL MATERIALS", en, *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* **247**, 194–218 (1975).

^[102]P. E. Hamrick, "MECHANICAL EFFECTS OF ACOUSTIC TRANSIENTS ON TOBACCO MOSAIC VIRUS", en, PhD thesis (Medical College of Virginia, 1968).

^[103]L. Wen et al., "Thermoacoustic Imaging and Therapy Guidance based on Ultra-short Pulsed Microwave Pumped Thermoelastic Effect Induced with Superparamagnetic Iron Oxide Nanoparticles", *Theranostics* **7**, 1976–1989 (2017).

^[104]L. Puranen and K. Jokela, "Radiation Hazard Assessment of Pulsed Microwave Radars", en, *Journal of Microwave Power and Electromagnetic Energy* **31**, 165–177 (1996).

^[105]V. H. Man et al., "Picosecond infrared laser-induced all-atom nonequilibrium molecular dynamics simulation of dissociation of viruses", en, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **18**, 11951–11958 (2016).

^[106]D. Osorio-González et al., "Receptor Binding Domain (RBD) Structural Susceptibility in the SARS-CoV-2 Virus Spike Protein Exposed to a Pulsed Electric Field", en, *Journal of Nuclear Physics, Material Sciences, Radiation and Applications* **8**, 177–182 (2021).

There is a body of work on coherent control of viral inactivation using picosecond laser exposure^[107]. Breaking viral capsids by exciting long-wavelength vibrations using Raman scattering has been reported experimentally^{[108][109][110]}, however these results have failed replication^[111]. The author has not investigated this mechanism in any detail. Molecular dynamics of ISRU has been considered^[112], (^[113] but without considering heat-bath damping). Interestingly, if the well-established 1 TW power density^[114] for mammalian cell damage by femtosecond laser is scaled linearly with time to the nanosecond regime, a power density similar to that of^[115] is found ($1 \text{ TW/m}^2 / (100 \text{ ps} / 0.3 \text{ ps}) = 3 \text{ GW/m}^2$).

Optical centrifuges use a rotating polarization to induce a dipole moment and spin up small molecules^{[116][117]}. Electrorotation^{[118][119][120][121]} of viruses has been reported^{[122][123][124]}, but as yet only in a non-destructive

low-speed sub-synchronous regime for sensing, using optical means to detect rotation - using the virion as a kind of electrostatic induction motor. High-frequency dielectrophoresis and electrostatic trapping of viruses has also been reported^[125], without suggestions of electrostatic damage, implying that conventional irreversible electroporation of viruses should require longer than 10 microseconds.

A rotational drag coefficient can be extracted from MD simulation^[126]. We simulated a 30 nm lipid liposome using the MARTINI coarse-grained^{[127][128][129]} lipid force fields with GROMACS^[130] torque measurement feature, kindly implemented by Kutzner^[131]. This suggests a maximum rotation frequency on the order of 10^3 , but this value requires so many assumptions that it's hardly worth mentioning.

- ^[107]X. Zhou et al., "Maximum relative excitation of a specific vibrational mode via optimum laser-pulse duration", en, *Physical Review B* **82**, 075433 (2010).
- ^[108]K.-T. Tsen et al., "Inactivation of viruses by laser-driven coherent excitations via impulsive stimulated Raman scattering process", *Journal of Biomedical Optics* **12**, 064030 (2007).
- ^[109]S.-W. D. Tsen et al., "Prospects for a novel ultrashort pulsed laser technology for pathogen inactivation", en, *Journal of Biomedical Science* **19**, 62 (2012).
- ^[110]S.-W. D. Tsen et al., "Studies of inactivation mechanism of non-enveloped icosahedral virus by a visible ultrashort pulsed laser", en, *Virology Journal* **11**, 20 (2014).
- ^[111]J. C. Wigle et al., "No effect of femtosecond laser pulses on DNA, protein, M13, or E. coli", in *Optical Interactions with Tissue and Cells XXII*, Vol. 7897 (Mar. 2011), p. 789716.
- ^[112]X. Zhou et al., "Maximum relative excitation of a specific vibrational mode via optimum laser-pulse duration", en, *Physical Review B* **82**, 075433 (2010).
- ^[113]E. C. Dykeman and O. F. Sankey, "Vibrational energy funneling in viruses-simulations of impulsive stimulated Raman scattering in M13 bacteriophage", eng, *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter: An Institute of Physics Journal* **21**, 505102 (2009).
- ^[114]U. K. Tirlapur and K. König, "Targeted transfection by femtosecond laser", en, *Nature* **418**, 290–291 (2002).
- ^[115]R. de Seze et al., "Repeated exposure to nanosecond high power pulsed microwaves increases cancer incidence in rat", en, *PLOS ONE* **15**, e0226858 (2020).
- ^[116]D. M. Villeneuve et al., "Forced Molecular Rotation in an Optical Centrifuge", *Physical Review Letters* **85**, 542–545 (2000).
- ^[117]M. Gupta and R. N. Zare, "Spinning molecules to bits", en, *Nature* **407**, 33–34 (2000).
- ^[118]W. M. Arnold and U. Zimmermann, "Rotating-Field-Induced Rotation and Measurement of the Membrane Capacitance of Single Mesophyll Cells of *Avena sativa*", en, *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung C* **37**, 908–915 (1982).
- ^[119]W. Arnold and U. Zimmermann, "Electro-rotation: development of a technique for dielectric measurements on individual cells and particles", en, *Journal of Electrostatics* **21**, 151–191 (1988).
- ^[120]K. L. Chan et al., "Electrorotation of liposomes: verification of dielectric multi-shell model for cells", en, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Lipids and Lipid Metabolism* **1349**, 182–196 (1997).
- ^[121]H. P. Schwan, "Dielectric spectroscopy and electro-rotation of biological cells", en, *Ferroelectrics* **86**, 205–223 (1988).
- ^[122]C. Dalton et al., "Analysis of parasites by electrorotation", en, *Journal of Applied Microbiology* **96**, 24–32 (2004).
- ^[123]J. Gimsa, "New Light-Scattering and Field-Trapping Methods Access the Internal Electric Structure of Submicron Particles, like Influenza Viruses", en, *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* **873**, 287–298 (1999).
- ^[124]J. Gimsa, "A comprehensive approach to electro-orientation, electrodeformation, dielectrophoresis, and electrorotation of ellipsoidal particles and biological cells", *Bioelectrochemistry (Amsterdam, Netherlands)* **54**, 23–31 (2001).
- ^[125]F. Grom et al., "Accumulation and trapping of hepatitis A virus particles by electrohydrodynamic flow and dielectrophoresis", en, *ELECTROPHORESIS* **27**, 1386–1393 (2006).
- ^[126]T. Hogg et al., "Evaluating the Friction of Rotary Joints in Molecular Machines", *Molecular Systems Design & Engineering* **2**, 235–252 (2017).
- ^[127]S. J. Marrink et al., "The MARTINI Force Field: Coarse Grained Model for Biomolecular Simulations", en, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **111**, 7812–7824 (2007).
- ^[128]K. J. Boyd and E. R. May, "BUMPY: A model-independent tool for constructing lipid bilayers of varying curvature and composition", *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **14**, 6642–6652 (2018).
- ^[129]Tsjerk, *Tsjerk/Insane*, Dec. 2020.
- ^[130]D. Van Der Spoel et al., "GROMACS: Fast, flexible, and free", en, *Journal of Computational Chemistry* **26**, 1701–1718 (2005).
- ^[131]C. Kutzner et al., "Keep It Flexible: Driving Macromolecular Rotary Motions in Atomistic Simulations with GROMACS", en, *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation* **7**, 1381–1393 (2011).

From^[132], the upper bound of a homogenous spherical virus with 10 MPa overall tensile strength appears to be about 10^9 Hz.^[133]

Almost all biological spectroscopy techniques have produced resonance-like artifacts at some point in the literature, and we suggest that even the most striking and competently-obtained absorption data should not necessarily be trusted implicitly. Trustworthiness probably depends most significantly on the quality of error analysis; many have made good use of otherwise unreliable techniques. However, particularly in this field, it seems most productive to use the most advanced techniques, those that are foolproof by their very nature. Based only on our experience of the literature, in order of decreasing reliability for resonance measurement:

- Background-free photothermal optical^{[134][135]}
- Time-domain spectroscopy (many advantages cited by^[136], including instant, drift-free capture of all frequencies and limited instrumentation artifacts),^{[137][138]}
- Raman or other non-photothermal optical (^[139] \neq ^{[140][141]}) and also ^[142], but we have no understand-

ing of how such artifacts could form

- Frequency-domain CW VNA absorption or reflection (^[143] \neq ^{[144][145]})^{[146][147]}.

Although not representative of careful, well-calibrated VNA testing because of the crudity of our homebrew spectrometer, we were able to produce many candidate resonances in our data with perfectly justifiable modifications to post-processing, which raises interesting (but not novel^[148],^{[149][150]}) questions regarding software development in such conditions.^[151]

Positive artifacts are very common when exposing organisms to electric fields, and extreme care in experimental design appears to be required to produce any meaningful result. Excellent best-practices guide-

^[132] K. A. Holsapple, "Spinning rods, elliptical disks and solid ellipsoidal bodies: Elastic and plastic stresses and limit spins", en, *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics* **43**, 733–742 (2008).

^[133] [📄/documents/optical_centrifuge.ipynb](#)

^[134] I. J. Bigio et al., "Microwave absorption spectroscopy of DNA", en, *Biopolymers* **33**, 147–150 (1993).

^[135] P. Mukherjee et al., "Broadband microwave absorption spectrometer for liquid media", *Review of Scientific Instruments* **59**, 2577–2582 (1988).

^[136] Y. Feldman et al., "Time domain dielectric spectroscopy study of biological systems", en, *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation* **10**, 728–753 (2003).

^[137] N. Axelrod et al., "Dielectric spectroscopy data treatment: I. Frequency domain", en, *Measurement Science and Technology* **15**, 755–764 (2004).

^[138] N. Miura et al., "Microwave dielectric study on bound water of globule proteins in aqueous solution", en, *Biopolymers* **34**, 357–364 (1994).

^[139] M. L. Swicord and C. C. Davis, "An optical method for investigating the microwave absorption characteristics of DNA and other biomolecules in solution", en, *Bioelectromagnetics* **4**, 21–42 (1983).

^[140] K. Foster et al., "'Resonances' in the dielectric absorption of DNA?", *Biophysical Journal* **52**, 421–425 (1987).

^[141] C. Gabriel et al., "Dielectric behavior of aqueous solutions of plasmid DNA at microwave frequencies", en, *Biophysical Journal* **55**, 29–34 (1989).

^[142] see Taylor (L. S. Taylor, "The mechanisms of athermal microwave biological effects", en, *Bioelectromagnetics* **2**, 259–267 [1981]) citing unpublished, personal communication - a textbook example of positive publication bias!

^[143] M. L. Swicord and C. C. Davis, "Microwave absorption of DNA between 8 and 12 GHz", en, *Biopolymers* **21**, 2453–2460 (1982).

^[144] K. Foster et al., "'Resonances' in the dielectric absorption of DNA?", *Biophysical Journal* **52**, 421–425 (1987).

^[145] C. Gabriel et al., "Dielectric behavior of aqueous solutions of plasmid DNA at microwave frequencies", en, *Biophysical Journal* **55**, 29–34 (1989).

^[146] M. J. Hagmann and O. P. Gandhi, "Substitution Method for Swept-Frequency Measurements of Dielectric Properties at Microwave Frequencies", *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* **30**, 103–106 (1982).

^[147] O. P. Gandhi et al., "Millimeter wave absorption spectra of biological samples", en, *Bioelectromagnetics* **1**, 285–298 (1980).

^[148] M. E. Monzani, "Blinding and Salting in Dark Matter Searches", en, 50.

^[149] I. A. G. Snellen et al., "Re-analysis of the 267-GHz ALMA observations of Venus: No statistically significant detection of phosphine", *arXiv:2010.09761 [astro-ph]* (2020).

^[150] M. A. Thompson, "The statistical reliability of 267 GHz JCMT observations of Venus: No significant evidence for phosphine absorption", *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society: Letters* **501**, L18–L22 (2020).

^[151] One solution might be to keep all data blind while developing the analysis software, and use synthetic data to calibrate. One objection might be that the data often inform the required calibration; we might retort that if the technique is so sensitive that the calibration procedure cannot be known beforehand, a different method with a higher SNR should be used.

lines and meta-analyses are available in^{[152][153][154][155]} and^[156].

Thermal effects appear to be most common. For instance, Manikowska^[157] showed a "highly significant (P > 0.001)" result, and state that "...under our experimental conditions, effects of heat stress and local heating are unlikely". This result was promptly refuted by^[158], who suggest a thermal artifact. Most critically, the localized hotspots created by microwave exposure are often almost impossible to measure. Ideally, experimental design should guarantee that even slight localized temperature rise above 3 C cannot occur^{[159][160][161]}, or use thermally-matched shams^[162].

FDTD simulation of exposure geometry and sample heating is now usually possible with free, open-source software and should be performed. A PyTorch-based FDTD library from^[163] was used in our study with some modification, but^[164] and^[165] are also excellent.

Next appear to be electrochemical^[166] effects; as noted above, metal ions from electrodes can wreak havoc. Even more obscure differences between positive and sham, such as very strange polymer surface effects observed by^[167], must be ruled out by experimental design.

If the effect exists, efficient use of the lower damping would seem to require more than one cycle of oscillation. It appears to be impossible at any input power to effectively drive a 10 GHz resonator in the lungs from outside the torso, partly because of the layer of conductive muscle that shields the chest cavity.

Open-ended waveguides^{[168][169][170]} or water bolus allow efficient coupling to the body. There is precedent for bronchoscopic^{[171][172]} or more invasive meth-

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- ^[152]Vijayalaxmi, "Biological and health effects of radiofrequency fields: Good study design and quality publications", en, *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis* **810**, 6–12 (2016).
- ^[153]Vijayalaxmi and T. J. Prihoda, "Comprehensive Review of Quality of Publications and Meta-Analysis of Genetic Damage in Mammalian Cells Exposed to Non-Ionizing Radiofrequency Fields", *Radiation Research* **191**, 20 (2018).
- ^[154]n. Vijayalaxmi and T. J. Prihoda, "Funding Source, Quality of Publications and Outcome in Genetic Damage in Mammalian Cells Exposed to Non-Ionizing Radiofrequency Fields", eng, *Radiation Research* **192**, 353–362 (2019).
- ^[155]C. K. Chou et al., "Radio frequency electromagnetic exposure: Tutorial review on experimental dosimetry", *Bioelectromagnetics: Journal of the Bioelectromagnetics Society, The Society for Physical Regulation in Biology and Medicine, The European Bioelectromagnetics Association* **17**, 195–208 (1996).
- ^[156]T. Batista Napotnik et al., "Effects of high voltage nanosecond electric pulses on eukaryotic cells (in vitro): A systematic review", en, *Bioelectrochemistry* **110**, 1–12 (2016).
- ^[157]E. Manikowska-Czerska et al., "Effects of 2.45 GHz microwaves on meiotic chromosomes of male CBA/CAY mice", en, *Journal of Heredity* **76**, 71–73 (1985).
- ^[158]C. V. Beechey et al., "Cytogenetic Effects of Microwave Irradiation on Male Germ Cells of the Mouse", *International Journal of Radiation Biology and Related Studies in Physics, Chemistry and Medicine* **50**, 909–918 (1986).
- ^[159]W. Grundler and F. Keilmann, "Sharp Resonances in Yeast Growth Prove Nonthermal Sensitivity to Microwaves", en, *Physical Review Letters* **51**, 1214–1216 (1983).
- ^[160]M. A. Epstein and H. F. Cook, "The Effects of Microwaves on the Rous No. 1 Fowl Sarcoma Virus", *British Journal of Cancer* **5**, 244–251 (1951).
- ^[161]N. K. Chemeris et al., "DNA damage in frog erythrocytes after in vitro exposure to a high peak-power pulsed electromagnetic field", en, *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis* **558**, 27–34 (2004).
- ^[162]O. P. Gandhi, "Some Basic Properties of Biological Tissues for Potential Biomedical Applications of Millimeter Waves", en, *Journal of Microwave Power* **18**, 295–304 (1983).
- ^[163]F. Laporte et al., "Highly parallel simulation and optimization of photonic circuits in time and frequency domain based on the deep-learning framework PyTorch", en, *Scientific Reports* **9**, 5918 (2019).
- ^[164]Warren et al., "A CUDA-based GPU engine for gprMax: Open source FDTD electromagnetic simulation software", en, *Computer Physics Communications* (2019) **10**.1016/j.cpc.2018.11.007.
- ^[165]T. Liebig, *openEMS - Open Electromagnetic Field Solver*.
- ^[166]K. P. Drees et al., "Comparative electrochemical inactivation of bacteria and bacteriophage", en, *Water Research* **37**, 2291–2300 (2003).
- ^[167]B Bergqvist et al., "Effect of microwave radiation on permeability of liposomes. Evidence against non-thermal leakage", en, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects* **1201**, 51–54 (1994).
- ^[168]P. Neelakantaswamy and A. Rajaratnam, "Open-Ended Circular Waveguide with a Curved Corrugated Disk at its Aperture as a Diathermy Applicator", *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* **30**, 2005–2008 (1982).
- ^[169]K. Nikita and N. Uzunoglu, "Analysis of the power coupling from a waveguide hyperthermia applicator into a three-layered tissue model", *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* **37**, 1794–1801 (1989).
- ^[170]S. C. P. Miet and C. P. H. Smiee, "14.5GHz Circular Waveguide Applicator for the Treatment of Skin Cancer", in *2018 Asia-Pacific Microwave Conference (APMC)* (Nov. 2018), pp. 1399–1401.
- ^[171]H.-B. Yuan et al., "Flexible bronchoscopy-guided microwave ablation in peripheral porcine lung: a new minimally-invasive ablation", *Translational Lung Cancer Research* **8**, 787–796 (2019).
- ^[172]F. Hojattollah and P. Punit, "Antenna Designs for Microwave Tissue Ablation", *Critical reviews in biomedical engineering* **46**, 495–521 (2018).

ods^{[173][174][175]}.

Dispersion and Brillouin precursors do offer a means to produce a significant improvement in loss through tissue, and the required electrical waveforms appear to be synthesizable by variable-impedance or stub transmission-line pulse shaping^{[176][177]}.

See supplemental for a cursory treatment of the Brillouin precursors.

A sawtooth might be the optimal waveform (see below). However, obtaining 10 GHz tones deep in the body is still very hard, and may require very complicated dispersive phased arrays^[178].

E. coli phage T4r was selected for biosafety reasons, and because of the large amount of experience^[179] and structural data available. T4 does not have a nucleocapsid; the charge distribution is likely much stronger than other RNA-like viruses Phi 6^[180]. Some more useful surrogates may include Pseudomonas Phi 6^[181], the lipid-

bearing PM2, PRD1 or PR4^[182] if the outer protein capsid is dissolved^{[183], [184]}; or synthetic lipid liposomes. Certain phages also allow efficient concentration without ultracentrifuge, either by PEG precipitation^[185] and settling, or via VIRADEL^{[186][187][188][189]}, by altering the zeta potential of a syringe filter.

Custom single-lipid liposome surrogates appear to be relatively easy to produce and fill with a DNA tracer by sonication and dehydration^{[190][191][192]}. We encountered one problem in removing unencapsulated DNA, which typically requires ultracentrifugation as precipitation of liposomes is difficult. However,^[193] appear to demonstrate that ethanol extraction is satisfactory - we have not tested this. This likely does not lead to DNA precipitation because of the lack of salt.

When phage is rapidly immersed in solution of differing osmotic strength, the active system that maintains osmotic equilibrium is overwhelmed, and the resulting pressure ruptures the capsid when it exceeds about 100 atm^[194]. By $\sigma = pr/2t$ $t = 5.7 \text{ nm}$ ^[195] and $r = 60 \text{ nm}$, capsid

^[173]L. Taylor, "Implantable radiators for cancer therapy by microwave hyperthermia", *Proceedings of the IEEE* **68**, 142–149 (1980).

^[174]L. S. Taylor et al., "Implantable microwave radiators for clinical hyperthermia", en, *Radio Science* **17**, 125S–133S (1982).

^[175]R. King et al., "The Electromagnetic Field of an Insulated Antenna in a Conducting Or Dielectric Medium", *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* **31**, 574–583 (1983).

^[176]W. Margulis and R. Persson, "Coaxial electrical pulse shaper for picosecond electronics", en, *Review of Scientific Instruments* **56**, 1586–1588 (1985).

^[177]B Worm and R Pregla, "Arbitrary Pulse Shape Synthesis via Nonuniform Transmission Lines", en, 5.

^[178]A. Y. Cheung, "Microwave and radiofrequency techniques for clinical hyperthermia.", *The British Journal of Cancer. Supplement* **5**, 16–24 (1982).

^[179]E. Kellenberger, "History of phage research as viewed by a European", en, *FEMS Microbiology Reviews* **17**, 7–24 (1995).

^[180]Naming organisms with greek letters makes literature review somewhat more difficult, because many search engines do not support Unicode.

^[181]K. Gallandat and D. Lantagne, "Selection of a Biosafety Level 1 (BSL-1) surrogate to evaluate surface disinfection efficacy in Ebola outbreaks: Comparison of four bacteriophages", *PLoS ONE* **12** (2017) [10.1371/journal.pone.0177943](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0177943).

^[182]K. H. Lundstrom et al., "Lipid-containing Bacteriophage PR4: Structure and Life Cycle", en, *Journal of General Virology* **43**, 583–592 (1979).

^[183]H. M. Kivelä et al., "Bacteriophage PM2 Has a Protein Capsid Surrounding a Spherical Proteinaceous Lipid Core", *Journal of Virology* **76**, 8169–8178 (2002).

^[184]J. Caldentey et al., "Dissociation of the Lipid-Containing Bacteriophage PRD1: Effects of Heat, pH, and Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate", en, *Virology* **194**, 557–563 (1993).

^[185]K. R. Yamamoto et al., "Rapid bacteriophage sedimentation in the presence of polyethylene glycol and its application to large-scale virus purification", en, *Virology* **40**, 734–744 (1970).

^[186]M. Delbruck, *THE GROWTH OF BACTERIOPHAGE AND LYSIS OF THE HOST*.

^[187]S. R. Farrah, "Chemical factors influencing adsorption of bacteriophage MS2 to membrane filters.", *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* **43**, 659–663 (1982).

^[188]R. Armon et al., "A highly efficient second-step concentration technique for bacteriophages and enteric viruses using ammonium sulfate and Tween 80", en, *Canadian Journal of Microbiology* **34**, 651–655 (1988).

^[189]D. C. Roepke et al., "An Adsorption-Elution Technique for the Recovery of Influenza Virus from Water", *Avian Diseases* **33**, 649–653 (1989).

^[190]D. W. Deamer and G. L. Barchfeld, "Encapsulation of macromolecules by lipid vesicles under simulated prebiotic conditions", en, *Journal of Molecular Evolution* **18**, 203–206 (1982).

^[191]D. Putri et al., "OPTIMIZATION OF MIXING TEMPERATURE AND SONICATION DURATION IN LIPOSOME PREPARATION", *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Community* **14**, 79–85 (2017).

^[192]S. Mutalik et al., "Liposome encapsulated soy lecithin and cholesterol can efficiently replace chicken egg yolk in human semen cryopreservation medium", *Systems biology in reproductive medicine* **60** (2014) [10.3109/19396368.2014.902521](https://doi.org/10.3109/19396368.2014.902521).

^[193]Floris Laporte, "Novel architectures for brain-inspired photonic computers", PhD thesis ().

^[194]A. Cordova et al., "Osmotic Shock and the Strength of Viral Capsids", en, *Biophysical Journal* **85**, 70–74 (2003).

^[195]W. Baschong et al., "Head structure of bacteriophages T2 and T4", eng, *Journal of Ultrastructure and Molecular Structure Research* **99**, 189–202 (1988).

strength should be about 53 MPa, less than the 100 to 300 MPa cited by^[196].

0.2 Experiment notes

The original paper by Yang et al used plaque assays and RT-PCR to measure envelope damage. Quantification of viral titer is a thoroughly solved problem, which did not justify the amount of time we spent developing the below procedures.

Although not sensitive to changes in infectivity, we used an amplification-free fluorescent dsDNA detection method, exactly as suggested by^[197], using a custom photon-counting reader and a 1:1 mix of viral solution with 1/4000 Biotium GelGreen (a safe Acridine Orange (N-alkylacridinium) based fluorophore).

This was a very convenient (stable over long periods of time, requires no host culture) and sufficiently sensitive (titers down to 10^8 of T4 (170 kbp dsDNA)) assay both for capsid damage and, by melting the capsid with an autoclave, for general virus titer estimation, far faster and less laborious^[198] than high-throughput plaque assays evaluated^{[199][200]}. More useful enveloped viral surrogates like Phi6 are RNA and a lower sensitivity can be expected.^[201]

This assay works because the fluorophore drastically changes fluorescence intensity and lifetime when in complex with DNA^{[202][203]}, and the large size of the GelGreen molecule prevents diffusion through intact membranes.

While their bandwidth is narrow, very cheap 0.5" laser line thin-film filters still work great for both excitation and emission for fluorescence techniques. Blue LEDs [Cree XLamp XP-E2 Blue Starboard] are then sufficient

for excitation (though high CRI white LEDs emit more 480 nm blue, green leakage is too high). Dichroic mirrors are unnecessary for this application. Use a 1 mm plastic fiber optic at right angles to decrease excitation light scattering. Beware material autofluorescence - custom Lexan cuvettes unexpectedly overwhelmed the DNA signal (final set: [emission: Tiffen Orange 16 gel^[204] in series with Thorlabs FL05532, 532nm, 10 nm FWHM] [Edmund 28432, 486 nm]). A surplus Hammamatsu R4220 with HC123 current-limiting base at maximum sensitivity was used. A low-voltage silicon photomultiplier like ON Semi's C-Series SiPMs will probably be sufficient in most cases.

PMT dark counts and ambient light were removed by synchronous photon counting^[205] - add when light is on, subtract when light is off. The fluorescence excitation light was 50% square-wave modulated at 100 khz. This cannot be done with luminescence. Further filtering could be done by fluorescence lifetime discrimination.

Many luminescent assays require high-performance DSLR CCDs capable of several minute exposures.^[206] use ImageJ^[207] to stack frames from standard CMOS video cameras. In our testing, this was ineffective with expensive, high-quality industrial CMOS cameras, but extremely effective with webcams and ELP-brand cameras. Performance of such a stacked video approached that of the photomultiplier.

A number of other capsid damage assays were evaluated. However, these initial tests were marred by the 1 uL sample volume in our initial cuvette attempts, our use of a domestic fridge to store phage, which unexpectedly froze regularly overnight, apparently reducing phage titer, along with our accidental use of T4r+ (not an "improved" T4r, as we believed, but rather a mutation away from rapid-lysis, meaning that the lysis behavior is far slower (see^[208]). In our testing, lysis of T4r+ only occurred on plaque plates [where culture growth and log

^[196] I. L. Ivanovska et al., "Bacteriophage capsids: Tough nanoshells with complex elastic properties", en, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **101**, 7600–7605 (2004).

^[197] J. Xu et al., "Quantification of Adeno-Associated Virus with Safe Nucleic Acid Dyes", en, *bioRxiv*, 2020.02.27.968636 (2020).

^[198] "Fast turnaround time has always been important to me. Mistakes are unavoidable, so I always wanted an apparatus that would allow mistakes to be corrected as rapidly as possible." (S. Chu, "The manipulation of neutral particles", en, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **70**, 22 [1998])

^[199] S. Chhibber et al., "Simple drop cast method for enumeration of bacteriophages", en, *Journal of Virological Methods* **262**, 1–5 (2018).

^[200] K. M. Kauffman and M. F. Polz, "Streamlining standard bacteriophage methods for higher throughput", en, *MethodsX* **5**, 159–172 (2018).

^[201] Biotium, *Selected References for GelRed and GelGreen*.

^[202] A. I. Dragan et al., "SYBR Green I: Fluorescence Properties and Interaction with DNA", en, *Journal of Fluorescence* **22**, 1189–1199 (2012).

^[203] A. I. Dragan et al., "Characterization of PicoGreen Interaction with dsDNA and the Origin of Its Fluorescence Enhancement upon Binding", English, *Biophysical Journal* **99**, 3010–3019 (2010).

^[204] A. C. Peed, "Transmission of Wratten filters", in *CRC handbook of chemistry and physics*, Vol. 85 (CRC press, 2004).

^[205] F. T. Arecchi et al., "Measurement of Low Light Intensities by Synchronous Single Photon Counting", *Review of Scientific Instruments* **37**, 942–948 (1966).

^[206] J. Balsam et al., "Image stacking approach to increase sensitivity of fluorescence detection using a low cost complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) webcam", en, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* **171-172**, 141–147 (2012).

^[207] C. A. Schneider et al., "NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image analysis", en, *Nature Methods* **9**, 671–675 (2012).

^[208] A. D. Hershey, "Spontaneous Mutations in Bacterial Viruses", en, *Cold Spring Harbor Symposia on Quantitative Biology* **11**, 67–77 (1946).

stage infectivity is maintained for many days]).

E. coli produces the enzyme β -galactosidase to break lactose into glucose for later metabolism. A luciferase-based luminescent assay, Promega Beta-Glo, was evaluated, as described in^[209]. One component of the beta-glo contains a proprietary detergent designed to lyse cells^[210] and expose the enzyme, counterproductive for phage use. Perhaps the detergent is not effective on bacteria, or the paper substrate that was used in the previous work was sufficient to bind the detergent. The detergent could perhaps be removed with BioBeads if this is desired.

While undoubtedly essential and very effective for its intended purpose (accurately quantifying lac operon activity), because of ambiguities in the rise and decay of the luminescence signal, short shelf life after the two components are mixed, oxygen depletion in small cuvettes, concerns regarding the detergent, and cost, Beta-Glo compared unfavorably to direct fluorescence or X-Gal for this specific application.

Positive control samples were put in a commercial pressure cooker to autoclave for 20 minutes in an Eppendorf tube: the pressure was released after the cycle to prevent dilution. The fluorophore was added after autoclaving.

We hoped to shape the nanosecond pulse into a high-voltage 10 GHz tone to drive the virus. This requires an

edge faster than 100 ps. It appears to be difficult, but not impossible^[211] to make spark gaps produce such fast edges without high-pressure^{[212][213][214]} or building the gap into a Marx^[215] pulse-forming line.

Avalanche transistors appear to be the easiest way to produce high power sub-100 picosecond pulses. We stole an avalanche Marx design verbatim from Li et al (^{[216][217]}), which allows large, fast pulses to be produced from lower voltage supplies (albeit requiring somewhat costly capacitors). 2N5551 transistors used to be commonly used for this purpose.^{[218][219][220]}; Oak's test circuit

In both of our final experimental setups, non-grounded, single-sided coplanar waveguides were used as exposure chambers, inspired by the CPWG heater of^{[221][222]} describe a very similar arrangement.

A programmable syringe withdrew and pumped approximately 50 μ L of fluid at a constant rate through one of the coplanar channels, via a 4 cm long silicone capillary (McMaster-Carr #51845K65) immersed in a 1.5 mL centrifuge tube using a 26 Ga Luer-lock (#6710A76). Forcing phage through the capillary is similar to lysis with a French pressure cell press, but no such effects were obviously seen.

FDTD simulations showed a significant decrease in field.^[223] and^[224] provide a good review of pulse exposure cells and a design which is much better than ours

^[209]S. Burnham et al., "Towards rapid on-site phage-mediated detection of generic *Escherichia coli* in water using luminescent and visual read-out", en, *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry* **406**, 5685–5693 (2014).

^[210]R. Hannah, "BETA-GLO® ASSAY SYSTEM: A LUMINESCENT beta-GALACTOSIDASE ASSAY FOR MULTIPLE CELL TYPES AND MEDIA", en, 4 (2003).

^[211]J. Lehr et al., *Fundamental physical considerations for ultrafast spark gap switching* (Feb. 1998), p. 20.

^[212]C. J. Brooker and P. D. Smith, "1 kHz, 25 kV output, sub-150 ps risetime gas spark gap and antenna", in *Digest of Technical Papers. Tenth IEEE International Pulsed Power Conference*, Vol. 1 (July 1995), 755–760 vol.1.

^[213]B. Martin et al., "Design of an ultra-compact UWB pulse former", in *2007 16th IEEE International Pulsed Power Conference*, Vol. 1 (June 2007), pp. 464–467.

^[214]W. Cravey et al., "Picosecond High Pressure Gas Switch Experiment", en, in *Ninth IEEE International Pulsed Power Conference* (1993), p. 483.

^[215]M. M. Kekez, "Simple sub-50-ps rise-time high voltage generator", en, *Review of Scientific Instruments* **62**, 2923–2930 (1991).

^[216]C. Li et al., "Development and Simulation of a Compact Picosecond Pulse Generator Based on Avalanche Transistorized Marx Circuit and Microstrip Transmission Theory", *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science* **44**, 1907–1913 (2016).

^[217]C. Li et al., "Design and Development of a Compact All-Solid-State High-Frequency Picosecond-Pulse Generator", *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science* **46**, 3249–3256 (2018).

^[218]S. W. Thomas et al., "Avalanche transistor selection for long-term stability in streak camera sweep and pulser applications", en, in *19th Intl Congress on High-Speed Photography and Photonics* (Apr. 1991), p. 77.

^[219]V. Rai and M. Shukla, "A high-voltage pulser circuit with subnanosecond rise time", *Review of Scientific Instruments* **65**, 2134–2136 (1994).

^[220]L. Jinyuan et al., "High voltage fast ramp pulse generation using avalanche transistor", en, *Review of Scientific Instruments* **69**, 3066–3067 (1998).

^[221]J. J. Shah et al., "Microwave dielectric heating of fluids in an integrated microfluidic device", en, *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering* **17**, 2224–2230 (2007).

^[222]J. F. Kolb et al., "Nanosecond pulsed electric field generators for the study of subcellular effects", en, *Bioelectromagnetics* **27**, 172–187 (2006).

^[223]D. Arnaud-Cormos et al., "Microchamber Setup Characterization for Nanosecond Pulsed Electric Field Exposure", *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* **58**, 1656–1662 (2011).

^[224]S. Kohler et al., "Characterization of a TEM cell-based setup for the exposure of biological cell suspensions to high-intensity nanosecond pulsed electric fields (nsPEFs)", in *2012 IEEE/MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest* (June 2012), pp. 1–3.

and should be used instead.^{[225] [226]}

The fluor-meter printed a constant stream of results, all within the random error between capture windows $\sigma = 0.5$ kcounts. Only after most of the data was taken was it realized how dumb this was.

Data rounded to the nearest thousand photon counts per 10 seconds.

If a fast laser is available, Auston switches appear to be equally effective.

Repeatability between test conditions was not terrific. The source of the ~5000 count variation between some equivalent samples, and between "blank" and "sham", is not known.

Background ('blank', in notes) readings measure the amount of DNA present in the phage culture tube before any treatment. 'sham' indicates a blank sample that was injected through the capillary identically to the treatment samples, except with either the VCO or Marx pulser disabled.

Ishii and Yanagida^[227], (Qin^[228]), find at a pH of 10.6, about 0.3x inactivation after a few minutes of incubation at 37 C, and almost complete loss after a few hours. The capsid is weakened greatly by the base, relying on the "clamp proteins" hoc and soc. It was thought that, if the phage capsid was weakened, it might be easier to destroy electrically. A sodium carbonate-bicarbonate buffer was used to raise the pH. Run 9 and Weakened show these results.

Note the difference in base inactivation timeline between Run 9 and Weakened. In one case, base inactivation is found exactly as predicted; little inactivation is found in the other. We cannot explain this result; it is possible that the buffer degraded somehow between experiments.

In no case did any field-exposed sample^[verify in notes] approach the 30 kcounts of the autoclave; therefore, we do not consider this a positive result.

Stock culture had titer 3×10^9 T4r.

The electrodes were only 1 oz copper thick (35 micrometers), but the engraved channel is significantly deeper.^[229] and simulations seem to suggest that this is not a serious problem, but it is possible that the field in much of the channel was much lower than predicted.

Results aggregated over the course of several months.

In all cases, a thermal effect was made implausible because of the short pulse duration; the total energy in the pulse train precluded heating above the capsid melting temperature, like^[230] - about 90 C for capsids^[231] and 50 C for envelopes^[232].

Only tubes 4 onwards are shown from Run 8 data because the capillary purging protocol was changed. In the final iteration, the autosampler was disconnected. The capillary was flushed with water; then the leuer lock was disconnected, air withdrawn into the syringe, and then purged through the capillary and fluidic channel.

In an early iteration of the experiment, the firmware and data analysis scripts randomly generated blinded sham and autoclave assignments and automatically treated the samples accordingly. It also printed blinded templates for pipetting. This was done partly in the hopes that massively oversampling the microwave absorption spectrometer across the range of physical tolerances would highlight any resonances.^[233]

However, as spectrometry was abandoned, this non-deterministic property caused considerable issues while troubleshooting the fluorescence detection system, and expedience^[234] prompted us to disable this system at run 9, defying best practices on blinded trials.

^[225]M. F. Iskander and T. S. Lind, "Electromagnetic coupling of coplanar waveguides and microstrip lines to highly lossy dielectric media", *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* **37**, 1910–1917 (1989).

^[226]The utility wcalc was used extensively

^[227]T. Ishii and M. Yanagida, "The two dispensable structural proteins (soc and hoc) of the T4 phage capsid; their purification and properties, isolation and characterization of the defective mutants, and their binding with the defective heads in vitro", en, *Journal of Molecular Biology* **109**, 487–514 (1977).

^[228]L. Qin et al., "Structure of the Small Outer Capsid Protein, Soc: a Clamp for Stabilizing Capsids of T4-like Phages", *Journal of molecular biology* **395**, 728 (2010).

^[229]J. F. Kolb et al., "Nanosecond pulsed electric field generators for the study of subcellular effects", en, *Bioelectromagnetics* **27**, 172–187 (2006).

^[230]M. A. Epstein and H. F. Cook, "The Effects of Microwaves on the Rous No. 1 Fowl Sarcoma Virus", *British Journal of Cancer* **5**, 244–251 (1951).

^[231]Y. Kawai, "Thermal transition profiles of bacteriophage T4 and its DNA", *The Journal of General and Applied Microbiology* **45**, 135–138 (1999).

^[232]C. Scholtissek, "Stability of infectious influenza A viruses to treatment at low pH and heating", en, *Archives of Virology* **85**, 1–11 (1985).

^[233]G. W. Oehlert, *A first course in design and analysis of experiments*, en (W.H. Freeman, New York, 2000).

^[234]laziness

For the Eppenwolf, the lower bound is the lowest voltage measured on the diode detector through the sweep (at 12 GHz), (raw unconverted voltage across frequency can be seen at https://firmware/eppenwolf/runs/phage_experiment_12/screenshot_192.168.0.38_2020-11-26_13:38:24.png - it is not recorded which detector this was seen at) multiplied by the FDTD results for the coplanar waveguide voltage to channel field scaling factor. The upper bound is the maximum voltage seen over the frequency sweep multiplied by the same FDTD factor.

The following is probably self-evident to all good scientists; unfortunately, we only learned it during this project, so it seems worthwhile to make explicit.

As noted later, this field reached a reasonable level of quality many decades ago, and many of the most troubling issues had already been encountered and addressed satisfactorily in published experimental designs^a.

In some cases, these are thoroughly characterized and described; field intensities are mapped, thermal profiles taken; even the dielectric properties of the media must be considered. But it seems that some workers continue to develop their own test arrangements; yet the studies are sometimes not so different as to require such customization.

This demands that the reader perform analysis anew to verify details of how the study was conducted, rather than simply evaluate its results; a waste of time on all counts.

By using yet another exposure cell, introducing a new set of unknown artifacts, we hamper this field; and so we encourage anyone who may wish to pursue similar results to not use this arrangement, but instead one of the existing, well-characterized exposure systems mentioned below or in the literature.

In this case, we were limited by budget - primarily the power amplifiers we have access to.

^aU. EPA, *Biological Effects Of RadioFrequency Radiation*, tech. rep. 600883026F (1984).

We are particularly excited by the prospect of using picosecond time-domain measurements not only to perform low-field-intensity steady state dielectric measurements or monitor the input pulse, as is now common practice, but to resolve the internal effects of a single high-voltage pulse on the virus in real time. Scan-

converter based transient digitizers, such as the Tektronix SCD-5000 series, appear to be the lowest-cost method of obtaining the >0.5 THz sampling bandwidths required, when the tube bandwidth is deconvolved.

Before the HMC732 was used, a misguided effort was spent in trying to develop an inexpensive wideband tunable oscillator for spectrometry. This will be chronicled in the GitHub repository.

1 Materials and methods

1.0.1 Main sample preparation

A stock preparation of 1:150 Biotium GelGreen was diluted to 1:4000 in a 15 mL Falcon tube.

With a Kartell 0.2 mL fixed-volume micropipette (McMaster-Carr #7015T17) connected to an autoclaved and flamed glass pipette, 0.2 mL of Carolina 124330 (early assay tests) or Carolina 124335 (electric field tests), titer 3×10^9 , was transferred into a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube. Field-tested phage was stored in a 4 C fridge for several months during the experiment.

stored in an aluminum light-tight bag was pipetted into the same 1.5 mL tube.

1.0.2 Main sample preparation

1.0.3 Nanosecond pulsed trials

A clone of Li et al's pulse generator was engraved with a 30 degree V-bit cutter onto a 1.6 mm double-sided 1 oz copper FR4 substrate. ATC 100B470JT500XT capacitors and FM417 transistors were used. This was powered by a HIA4 power supply at 330v.

Two coplanar waveguides, approximately 2.5 cm long, designed with 'wcalc'^[235], were similarly engraved into a single-sided 0.8 mm 1 oz copper FR4 substrate (MG chemicals). One waveguide (referred to as "0.2 mm channel") was 0.4 mm wide with 0.1 mm and 0.15 mm wide slots (asymmetric due to machining tolerances). The other was 0.4 mm wide with 0.03 and 0.06 mm slots.

The depth of the channels was not precisely known but considerably exceeded the copper thickness, as is reflected in the simulation.

[235] Wcalc.

Two end-launch SMA connectors were soldered to the waveguide; one connector was either terminated with a standard 50-ohm SMA terminator or left open, depending on the trial, and the other connected via semirigid coax (CCSMA-MM-086-12) to the pulse generator.

conclusion

A thin layer of silicone conformal coating was applied to the 0.2 mm waveguide to avoid the copper ion artifact, but this could not be done on the 0.03 mm waveguide.

1.0.4 FDTD tissue modelling

To determine penetration of waves in tissue, the four term Cole-Cole model^[236], https://github.com/ITIS-Foundation/electronics/simple_fDTD/fDTD_PCB_extensions/fDTD_PCB_extensions/tissue.py, was used with parameters from the IT.IS Foundation tissue database^[237]. The IT.IS Foundation computational phantom 'duke V3.0' was used,^[238].

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This paper would have been absolutely impossible without the support of thousands of open-source software packages, ranging from monolithic state-supported tools like Paraview to poorly-compensated but equally invaluable scripts like zonca/qucs^[239]. A special thanks to the dedicated authors that develop and maintain these tools, and especially to those who choose not to put them behind a paywall.

Hamming was wrong; despite the name above the abstract, this paper is of course entirely the result of circumstance, luck, and awesome friends.

Special thanks to Alexandra Elbakyan and Aaron Swartz.

^[236]C. Gabriel, *Compilation of the dielectric properties of body tissues at RF and microwave frequencies*. Tech. rep. (King's Coll London (United Kingdom) Dept of Physics, 1996).

^[237]I. Foundation, *Tissue Properties Database V4.0*, en, 2018.

^[238]I. Foundation, "Duke V3.0", en, (2014) 10.13099/VIP-DUKE-V3.0.

^[239]A. Zonca et al., "Modeling the frequency response of microwave radiometers with QUCS", *Journal of Instrumentation* 5, T12001–T12001 (2010).